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DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL AND CREATIVE THINKING IN STEM EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Critical thinking has been integrated into STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) curricula in many countries. This paper attempts to clarify the relationship with scientific literacy and conceptions and to discuss a framework for promoting students' critical thinking in teaching and learning physics.

An interactive approach of teaching physics forces students to work and think independently and enhance their active learning. Moreover, watching the real videos and doing video analysis of motions with the help of the program Tracker (video-analysis and simulations (VAS) method of solving problem tasks) helps them to see the discrepancies between their preconceptions, misconceptions and scientific concepts.

Using a standardized FCI (Force Concept Inventory) pre and post-tests we analyzed the teaching and learning processes during last three years. VAS method helps us to eliminate some student's misconceptions and enhanced students' conception connected with STEM education.

1 INTRODUCTION

The focus on processes of critical and creative thinking is required for next problem-solving, project-solving, decision-making and scientific research. The creative use and transfer of these thinking abilities in which students are expected to become more aware of their own thinking processes and better informed about the thinking strategies of others.

As Paul Hewitt claimed, "Science is a way of thinking as well as body of knowledge" [1]. Other authors declare that science requires the use of elementary clarification abilities to identify or formulate a question:

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- Basic support capabilities and elementary and advanced clarification abilities in order to search and select information in credible sources.
- The ability to design experiments and also the use of strategy and tactics abilities when presenting a report.

Therefore, it seems that critical thinking has an important role in science learning and consequently, in physics learning [2].

Critical Thinking is a major development goal of the science education industry. Projects/Tasks/Studies that require prediction, analysis, synthesizing, evaluation and reasoning, etc. [3] are all areas where critical thinking skills are a necessity [4, 5].

This is why we have turned our research attention to critical and conceptual thinking. Because, it's absolutely critical for us to further study problems in Newtonian mechanics.

2 METHODOLOGY

Students at the University of Žilina, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology (FEIT) attended compulsory Computational Physics exercises and lectures that were optional. The subject named 'Introduction to Physics' consists of 2 - 1 - 0 (lectures - exercises - labs) lessons per week. One lesson lasts 50 minutes. The term consists of 13 weeks.

We used Force Concept Inventory (FCI) test [6] to verify prior students' knowledge of Physics (Kinematics and Dynamics). It contained 30 qualitative multiple choice tasks that focused on conceptual understanding of Newtonian mechanics. FCI was given to students to find out prior knowledge level of physics at the beginning of the academic year. The pre-test was carried out at the beginning of the term during the first week and it was attended by 129, 122, 199 students (students participated in both pre and post-tests) in the academic years 2017/2018, 2018/2019 and 2019/2020, respectively. Post-test was carried out at the end of term after finishing the course 'Introduction to Physics'.

During lectures the VAS method of problem tasks was used, at the beginning of lecture problem tasks were critically discussed by students in small groups, then students have presented their views, they watched the real videos later on and finally, lecturer used video analysis of motions with the help of the program Tracker for the explanation of the natural laws in Newtonian mechanics.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As we can see in Fig. 1, results in Pre-test are comparable. We can declare, that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean (M) at the beginning of term (we used F-Test: Two Sample for Variances and t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Unequal Variances: 17/18: N = 129; M = 31.19; SD = 14.32; 18/19: N = 122; M = 33.97; SD = 14.63; 19/20: N = 199; M = 32.93; SD = 14.41). The same situation is also in Post-test: there is no statistically significant difference between the mean at the end of term (we used F-Test: Two Sample for Variances and t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Unequal Variances: 17/18: M = 39.10; SD = 16.20; 18/19: M = 41.31; SD = 16.50; 19/20: M = 39.40; SD = 16.54). But in the same academic year, there is statistically

significant difference between the mean of pre and post-test FCI score (we used t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means, $p < 1E-14$ (a.y.19/20)).

Fig. 1. Box Plots of Pre and Post-test FCI results in individual academic years – 17/18, 18/19, 19/20.

Fig. 2. Analysis of individual questions of FCI Pre-test results in individual academic years – 2017/18, 2018/19, 2019/20.

Fig. 3. Analysis of individual questions of FCI Post-test results in individual academic years – 2017/18, 2018/19, 2019/20.

Detailed analysis of individual questions helped us find some misconceptions, e.g.: “greater mass implies greater force” (questions: Q4, Q15, Q16, Q28) and “most active agent produces the greatest force” (questions: Q15, Q16, Q28) (Tab. 1). For explanation of the Newton's Third Law: Action/Reaction Pairs we used video of head-on collide of a truck with a small compact car.

Table 1. Analysis of particular questions in individual academic years

	Ac.year	The biggest of incorrect answers [%]			Correct answer [%]		
		2017/18	2018/19	2019/20	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20
Q4	Pre-test	72	69	76	23	28	20
	Post-test	41	40	44	57	56	53
Q15	Pre-test	58	58	55	19	21	26
	Post-test	49	41	43	42	49	42
Q16	Pre-test	24	32	30	61	48	55
	Post-test	15	12	18	71	78	71
Q28	Pre-test	49	46	46	27	31	30
	Post-test	26	21	32	62	66	59

To calculate the normalized average gain g we used Hake formula [7], where the difference between the total percentage of students in the Post-Test and the Pre-Test was divided by the difference between 100% and the percentage of students in the Pre-test:

$$g = \frac{Post_test - Pre_test [\%]}{100 - Pre_test [\%]} \quad (1)$$

The gain $0.3 < g < 0.7$ means teaching was effective (Tab. 2).

Table 2. Analysis of the normalized average gain g in individual academic years

	Academic year		
	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20
Q4	0.45	0.38	0.41
Q15	0.28	0.36	0.22
Q16	0.48	0.58	0.37
Q28	0.48	0.51	0.41

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Our research has pointed to the fact that the students entering to university have difficulties with conceptions of Newtonian mechanics. Deep analysis of some answers in Pre and Post FCI tests shows us that there are differences in knowledge of students at the end of term connected with using VAS method.

Future deeper analysis can help us to find and eliminate the misconceptions of the students and also to improve teaching methods and students' level of knowledge in the introductory courses of general Physics, mainly in the field of Mechanics. It can be useful for building of critical thinking of students in their future study of STEM.

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